

Quantifying the Extended Acceptance of Pioneering Art Music Through the Creation of Electroacoustic Music

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ABSTRACT

Since 2009, the laboratory to which the first author of this paper belongs has been running a workshop for creating electroacoustic music in collaboration with inexperienced people from various generations. The authors developed this workshop as a participatory art project activity in which instructors and participants collaborate to create a work of music following a workshop and perform it at a concert, and it has been operating as such since 2015. Although electroacoustic music is considered obscure and currently has few listeners or creators, the workshop saw many inexperienced participants enjoying making electroacoustic music. This paper details our study's verification of the hypothesis that participants' level of acceptance of "difficult music" increased after experiencing the workshops. The reason for attempting this verification is not to affirm contemporary music itself and impose existing values surrounding it on a diverse population, but to clarify the cognitive effects of electroacoustic music and create an educational method based on these effects. In this verification, a questionnaire using the semantic differential (SD) method was administered to the creators before and after creating music. The results showed that the creators' impressions of the listening materials improved after creating music.

1. INTRODUCTION

From the late 19th century to the early 20th century, music was divided into two branches: entertainment-oriented music and music that emphasized philosophical aspects. The latter is now known as "contemporary music" and is currently being taught in many music colleges as a cultural heritage inherited from Western classical music. Electroacoustic music, the subject of the authors' exploration and research, is a subtype of this contemporary form of music. The term electroacoustic music is used as a generic term for "concrete music," founded by Pierre Schaeffer (1910–

1995) in 1948, and "electronic music," founded by Karlheinz Stockhausen (1928–2007) and Herbert Eimert (1897–1972) in the early 1950s. Concrete music is made by using sounds produced from various objects that exist in our surroundings and fragmentary environmental sounds, amalgamating them together through montage compositions. In contrast, electronic music is composed using electronically generated sound materials.

The creational techniques of electroacoustic music, which is the generic name for these techniques, have made remarkable progress with the later development of music information processing technology as well as the advent of personal computers and their increased affordability. These techniques are still being created and taught at art and information technology universities. Although the term Desk Top Music has become widespread since the mid-1990s and a variety of digital audio workstation software has become available, electroacoustic music does not have many listeners or creators. The authors believe that this is because electroacoustic music, which is a contemporary music genre, gives the impression of being "difficult" for many people.

The authors started the "Denshi Onkyo People Project" [1] in 2015. This project consists of the following: (1) a workshop to produce electroacoustic music; (2) completion of post-collaborative work using the work completed by the participants; (3) performance of the completed work at a concert; and (4) CD production and profit sharing. This sequence of events was made into a work of art in the form of a participatory project. The inspiration for this project came from a long-running workshop on composing electroacoustic music for the inexperienced public, which the authors have been conducting since 2009.

The method and purpose of this activity are described in detail in Shibayama [2]. The purpose is to promote a shift from the general trend in the relationship between the creators and receivers of music, where the creators are few and the receivers are many, to a landscape where both the creators and the receivers are in high numbers.

In these workshops, we have noticed that the participants unanimously enjoy the creation of this type of electroacoustic music. In addition, it has been observed that the evaluation of works with more experimental elements of sound materials, such as futurist and electroacoustic music works, improved after the workshop. Therefore, it can be considered that the range of acceptance for "difficult music" has expanded following the workshop. However, it is

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unclear if the level of acceptance expands due to the experience of creation. In this study, we attempt to quantitatively verify this phenomenon.

The authors measured the changes in the participants' impressions of "difficult music" as they experienced creation. This was done by (1) listening to three existing works with a higher acoustic complexity than ordinary musical works; (2) answering a questionnaire using the semantic differential (SD) method about their impressions; (3) practicing the creation of electroacoustic music; (4) listening to the same works as in (2) after completion and answering questions about their impressions; and (5) comparing the questionnaire responses obtained before and after the creation of the music. The same adjective pairs were used in the SD method questionnaire before and after the creative experience, and factors were extracted from the results using factor analysis. Variations in these factors were compared using a two-factor analysis of variance.

This paper details an investigation into whether the experience of creating electroacoustic music makes people more familiar with musical works that are often perceived as "difficult."

2. STUDY BACKGROUND

The purpose of this study is to test the hypothesis that participants' experience in creating electroacoustic music positively changes their impressions of acoustically complex music.

2.1 Characteristics of Musical Sounds in Tonal Music

The authors believe that electroacoustic music, which they both create and study, has a high degree of complexity compared to ordinary music, which has a clear melody and chord structure. This is because electroacoustic music is often composed using unpitched sounds rather than musical sounds. Musical sounds are tuned sounds from musical instruments, while unpitched sounds are other untuned sounds. Ordinary music is composed of the former musical sounds and therefore usually has a clear structure of chords and melody. This musical sound is a tuned sound, and it has a pitch obtained from a fixed frequency. In addition, melodies and chords are composed of scales, which are sets of musical sounds with different pitches. Figure 1 shows the ratio of frequencies of scales according to just intonation. It shows the ratio of the frequencies of each pitch when the note "C," the root note of this scale, is set as 1. A melody is composed of these different pitches in time, and a chord structure is composed of a set of simultaneous tones and their chronological connection.

Figure 1. Ratio of frequencies in a just-intonation scale

The two different pitches are called an interval. The simpler the ratio of the frequency, the more harmonious the interval. A 1:1 unison or a 1:2 octave sound is so harmonious that it is difficult for the listener to distinguish between

the two distinct pitches that make up the interval. Triads used in music, such as CEG chords, are composed of simple frequency ratios of 1:5/4:3/2.

2.2 The Increased Complexity of Contemporary Music

Contemporary music emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, abandoning these traditional tonalities in favor of the twelve-tone technique, in which all twelve notes in an octave are treated equally. Naturally, the equal treatment of the 12 notes within an octave has led to the use of chords with complex pitch relationships. As a result, the frequency ratios of chord structures within a work are much more complex than in conventional tonal music. "Risveglio Di Una Citta," composed by the Italian futurist Luigi Russolo (1885–1947) in 1913, is another experiment in such complex music genres. This work demonstrates noise music composed by noise instruments called the Intonarumori. The Intonarumori were able to generate noise through weak currents and mechanical devices. This noise music fundamentally abandoned the concept of a musical scale that conventional music developed. The electroacoustic music that the authors are currently researching uses unpitched sounds rather than musical sounds, and it is considered to be positioned between conventional and noise music.

At first glance, these music compositions seem unrelated, but Nattiez viewed them in terms of their complexity, placing white noise, the aggregate of all frequencies, along a straight line as the limit of complexity [3].

2.3 The Relationship Between Pleasure and Complexity During Music Listening

Berlyne proposed the optimal complexity model [4] and showed the relationship between high complexity and pleasant and unpleasant impressions with an inverted-U hypothesis (see Figure 2). According to the inverted-U hypothesis, the x-axis indicates the value of complexity, and the y-axis indicates the value of pleasure.

Berlyne proposed that for the listener to derive pleasure from music, the music must be moderately complex. The model indicates that excessively high or excessively low complexity in music may significantly reduce the listener's pleasure value. This state of low complexity in music may be the case where a temporal structure is created only by overlying simple intervals, such as unisons or octaves, or where the listener can completely predict what will happen at which point in time, like the second hand on a clock.

As mentioned above, electroacoustic music uses unpitched and environmental sounds as sound materials. Because unpitched sounds have a much more complex overtone structure compared to musical sounds, they have greater frequency complexity and perceptual difficulties compared to ordinary music composed of musical sounds.

Figure 2. Berlyne's inverted-U hypothesis [4]

2.4 Electroacoustic Music Creation Workshops

Since 2009, the laboratory to which the authors belong has held workshops for the public to create electroacoustic music, which people tend to consider a difficult subgenre [2]. The purpose of this workshop is to share the awareness that pioneering works of art, which tend to be perceived as difficult to understand, are easy to create and to encourage viewers of art to take the position of creators.

The workshop's production instructions are:

- 1) Record multiple sound materials from items brought by the participants;
- 2) Distribute the recorded sound material to the participants' individual computers;
- 3) Fragment the distributed sound material and edit it using speed and pitch changes, inversion, normalization, and montage;
- 4) Finish a piece of work of 10 to 20 s in duration.

For recording in step 1, participants were asked to freely bring objects that they felt sounded good or they had a particular attachment to and would like to use in their work. For example, the sounds of participants' everyday cooking utensils and cleaning tools, stationery, and empty cans and bottles that are no longer needed have been recorded. While participants were recording, the authors suggested that instead of playing with the objects they had brought, they should try to obtain a variety of sounds that can be created by these objects. For example, the sounds of impacts, deformation, and scraping. In this way, recording a variety of sound materials from a single object has the potential to create a greater variety of expression in the production of a work. A characteristic feature of this production-instruction method by the authors is that in step 3 of the process, the participants were instructed to capture the impressions of fragmented sound bites using metaphors such as A) high/low, B) hard/soft, C) cold/warm, and D) smooth/rough and to be aware of these contrasts while producing their work. After completing the work in step 4, the professional composer who taught the workshop completes the work for each piece, respecting the individuality of the 5–10 works created by the participants. After the completion of this work, it is performed in a concert as a collaborative production. We plan to resume this activity after the COVID-19 pandemic and work on designing methods to encourage more active and long-term

participation for continued creation and collaboration following the workshop.

In this workshop, participants were asked to listen to electroacoustic and noise music works as resource material before and after their creation. It was often observed that their impression became more positive after completing their works. Therefore, the creative experience in this workshop increased the participants' receptivity to complexity in music. This may be another way of saying that their "*Kansei*," that is, their emotional response to creativity through images [5], has expanded.

This transition indicates that the vertex of Berlyne's inverted-U hypothesis has shifted to the right for each participant. As shown in Figure 3, this transition is a process that expands the participants' sensibility to recognize listening materials that were previously not identified as "music" [2, 6].

Therefore, the authors believe that creating music could improve the participants' positive impressions of music, even if that music is often regarded as difficult. To verify this, the change in impression was investigated using a quantitative method.

Figure 3. *Kansei*'s process of expansion [6]

2.5 Originality of this Study

In the extant literature, many references have been made to individual differences in the acceptance of works of art, which depend on the knowledge of art theory and history of art connoisseurs and the education that these individuals have received [7, 8, 9]. Individual differences in this acceptance may relate to difficulty in viewing and understanding a work of art if one does not adequately understand art theory and history [7], and education, especially that provided at home, shapes aesthetic tastes and preferences [9]. In addition, a model has been proposed in which the acquisition of knowledge and experience aids understanding while viewing the work of art, generating a positive impression [10, 11]. However, it can be said that the understanding of the arts is polysemous, and it is unclear to what extent knowledge, experience, or educational background may be a factor in creating a positive impression.

Museums usually include a caption with the work being presented, which includes the name of the work, the artist's name, the year it was created, and the materials that were used. In addition, the exhibition venues are actively equipped with supplementary explanatory panels on the artworks from an educational point of view. These accompanying pieces of information aid the understanding of the viewer and play a role in the formation of positive impressions. However, of course, knowing this accompanying information and what you receive when you face and view the work itself are two completely different experiences in terms of the amount of information being presented. Therefore, facing the work itself is an important part of the

process of understanding it. However, it may be very difficult to appreciate the work itself and understand what is being expressed in contemporary art, which is not easy to categorize due to its innovative ideas, abstract content, and the technological developments achieved via computing. What is important in such situations is that the viewer derives their own understanding from the work itself, rather than rely on an understanding centered on the accompanying information in the work. This is synonymous with encouraging divergent thinking in STEAM education [12] and is expected to lead to a transformation of the viewers' active viewing attitudes and the formation of diverse values.

We are interested in the type of understanding that the viewer receives via forming their own understanding of a work. Therefore, we consider the differences that may exist in the understanding of works between experienced artists and beginners. Compared to beginners, professional artists are thought to be able to better understand the background of an artwork, such as the technical ingenuity in the process of creating the work and the effort that was required. With this understanding of the creative process, one can make a relative comparison of one's own creative experience and impression when viewing a work of art, including its creative background. Whether or not the background of the work's creation is known may have an impact on the evaluation of the work at the time of viewing.

The authors are involved in electroacoustic music research and creative education. Research on electroacoustic music has traditionally focused on describing its complex musical structure, starting with its founder Pierre Schaeffer [13, 14, 15]. Conversely, quantitative verification of the cognitive aspects of complex works, such as how they are perceived by listeners and what factors make a positive impression on them, is an unexplored area. This study quantitatively examines how the impressions of works that are considered to be "difficult" change after the experience of creating related works, and we consider a large population with no experience of creating such works.

3. EXPERIMENT

This experiment was conducted with students who were making electroacoustic music for the first time in the Department of Informatics, to which the authors belong. The experiment was not conducted during the workshop for two reasons:

- A) A sufficient response time could not be allocated within the implementation time frame.
- B) The inability to hold a face-to-face workshop due to COVID-19.

Teaching creative work in class differs from workshops in terms of the implementation procedures, such as the creative period. However, we believe that creative teaching methods and creations themselves are similar and have several advantages when it comes to conducting experiments. For example, a workshop may have approximately 10 participants, but a class may acquire data from an even larger number of people.

In the future, when workshops can be conducted, we will verify the differences in the results of the experiments conducted in the class.

3.1 Purpose

The experiment requires participants to listen to a work of music with high acoustical complexity before and after the creation of electroacoustic music, and obtains their impressions of the music using the SD method questionnaire. The purpose of the experiment is to determine the changes in impressions before and after the creation of electroacoustic music.

3.2 Date

The experiment was conducted twice: the first pre-survey was conducted on 14/6/2022 and the post-survey on 21/6/2022; the second pre-survey was conducted on 12/7/2022 and the post-survey on 19/7/2022.

3.3 Participants

There were 130 participants (male: 110; female: 20) with an average age of 18.81.

3.4 Creation of Electroacoustic Music

Participants created electroacoustic music for one week. The sound material used for the creation was provided by the experimenter. Participant edits and montages provided sound material. Applying speed changes, pitch changes, and reverse playback are examples of effect processing used in the creation process. The final product was 20 s of electroacoustic music.

3.5 Works Used in the Experiment

The experiment used the following three works as listening materials:

- Sample 1) *Étude aux Chemins de Fer* (1948)
- Sample 2) *Risveglio Di Una Citta* (1913)
- Sample 3) *Earth Nazareth* (2001)

Sample 1 is the world's first work of electroacoustic music, composed by Pierre Schaeffer. Sample 2 is the world's first musical work to use noise and was composed by Luigi Russolo. Sample 3 is a musical work by one of the leading contemporary noise music writers, Merzbow (1956–).

The reasons for selecting these three works are as follows:

- 1) High acoustic complexity of the sound materials used in the work;
- 2) It is a representative work among works that use unpitched sounds and noise; and
- 3) The three works have different rhythms and ranges, therefore producing different results.

Samples 1 and 2 do not use modern music information processing technology. However, Sample 1 uses sound materials such as locomotive steam exhaust, running sounds, and bird calls as short sound fragments of approximately 1 s or sounds that last approximately 5 to 20 s. These sound fragments are connected and composed in a variety of ways in the work, such that many rhythmic

changes can be experienced. The sound range of this work is centered on the frequency in the mid-to-low range, with some frequencies in the high range. In contrast, Sample 2 uses the Intonarumori of noise instruments, and the continuous noise resonates from the beginning to the end of the work. The pitch of the continuous noise gradually changes or is overlaid with different repetitive noisy fragments. The sound range of this work is dominated by a mid-to-low range frequency, with almost no high-range frequency. Sample 3 uses the more modern music information processing technology when compared to Samples 1 and 2. It makes heavy use of very rough and strong noises. The sound range of this work is wide - from a high to a low range, and every range is full of energy.

3.6 Procedure

The experimental procedure is as follows:

- 1) We prepared three listening materials and asked the participants to answer a 12-item questionnaire based on the SD method about their impressions of each listening material before creating an electroacoustic work.
- 2) After one work was played, the participants were allowed 1 min to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaires were collected in this format for three works.
- 3) After one week of creation, we asked the participants to provide their impressions of each of the three works using the same procedure.

The playback order of the listening material was changed before and after the creation process. In addition, the questionnaire randomly changed the order of the adjective pair-response items, as well as the left and right sides of the scale, before and after creation.

3.7 Questionnaire Answer Items

Responses were obtained on a seven-point scale (1–7) using 12 adjective pairs. The adjective pairs used in the experiment were selected with reference to a series of experiments by Kitamura et al. on factorial invariance in tonal expressions using Japanese [16]. In this series of experiments, it was confirmed that regardless of the sound source, including the various music, noise, or voice sources, three factors tend to be invariably extracted when questionnaires using the SD method are utilized, and factor analysis was conducted for the “pleasant factor,” “metallic factor,” and the “powerful factor.” Therefore, the authors selected adjective pairs to avoid bias toward specific factors.

The 12 adjectives that were listed are as follows. The “pleasant factor”: (1) easy–difficult, (2) clear–muddy, (3) simple–complex, (4) pleasant–unpleasant, (5) smooth–rough; the “metallic factor”: (6) hard–soft, (7) metallic–deep, (8) shrill–calm, (9) sharp–dull; and the “powerful factor”: (10) clamorous–quiet, (11) strong–weak, (12) powerful–unsatisfactory.

4. RESULTS

The purpose of this study is to verify that the experience of creating electroacoustic music improves the impressions of such works, even if the music is often perceived

	Average	Before	After
(1)	easy–difficult**	5.315	4.454
(2)	clear–muddy**	5.652	4.593
(3)	simple–complex**	5.039	4.113
(4)	pleasant–unpleasant**	5.601	4.431
(5)	smooth–rough**	6.164	4.751
(6)	hard–soft**	2.362	3.425
(7)	metallic–deep**	2.036	3.556
(8)	shrill–calm**	2.371	3.356
(9)	sharp–dull**	2.205	3.825
(10)	clamorous–quiet**	1.444	2.944
(11)	strong–weak**	2.111	3.325
(12)	powerful–unsatisfactory**	2.665	3.621

Table 1. The average of evaluation values in Sample 1 (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$)

	Average	Before	After
(1)	easy–difficult*	5.102	4.683
(2)	clear–muddy	5.486	5.651
(3)	simple–complex	4.299	4.539
(4)	pleasant–unpleasant**	5.545	4.744
(5)	smooth–rough*	5.257	4.802
(6)	hard–soft**	3.068	3.674
(7)	metallic–deep**	4.312	4.796
(8)	shrill–calm**	3.496	4.104
(9)	sharp–dull**	3.573	4.269
(10)	clamorous–quiet*	1.921	2.295
(11)	strong–weak	2.299	2.369
(12)	powerful–unsatisfactory	2.750	2.700

Table 2. The average of evaluation values in Sample 2 (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$)

	Average	Before	After
(1)	easy–difficult	5.481	5.671
(2)	clear–muddy	5.876	5.939
(3)	simple–complex	4.993	5.251
(4)	pleasant–unpleasant*	6.192	5.845
(5)	smooth–rough	5.892	5.796
(6)	hard–soft	2.374	2.550
(7)	metallic–deep	3.173	3.161
(8)	shrill–calm**	1.938	2.305
(9)	sharp–dull*	1.587	1.890
(10)	clamorous–quiet	1.233	1.405
(11)	strong–weak	1.817	1.907
(12)	powerful–unsatisfactory	2.014	2.142

Table 3. The average of evaluation values in Sample 3 (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$)

as difficult to understand. To test this hypothesis, we analyze changes in the following two evaluation criteria.

Verification 1) The evaluation value of adjectives belonging to the pleasant factor decreased (e.g., (4) pleasant–unpleasant was changed to “pleasant,” that is, the evaluation value approached “1”).

Verification 2) The evaluation value of the adjectives belonging to the metallic/powerful factor increased (e.g., (10) clamorous–quiet was changed to “quiet,” that is, the evaluation value approached “7”).

We believe that these verifications confirm the improvement of positive impressions. For Verification 1, because the pleasant factor is an evaluation of a pleasant impression of the listening material, a decrease in this rating value signifies an improvement in its positive impression. For Verification 2, the improvement of the metallic and powerful factor can be seen as a reduction in the discomfort inherent in the unpitched sounds or noise, indicating an improvement in the positive impression of the pieces. For example, the metallic factor (9) sharp–dull can be interpreted as a reduction of unpleasant impressions when listening to a noise by perceiving it as being less sharp. The flow of analysis of this experiment was initially to check whether the three assumed factors (pleasant, metallic, and powerful) can be extracted based on the results of the SD-method questionnaire. Next, a two-factor analysis of variance is performed to verify the changes before and after creation.

Initially, a factor analysis based on the maximum likelihood method was performed on the evaluation values used in the questionnaire. Two or three factors were extracted from the results of a parallel analysis using the minimum average partial. The total value of items with a factor loading of 0.40 or more for each factor was utilized as the evaluation scale. When considering two factors, they were referred to as the (1) pleasant and (2) metallic/powerful factors. In the case of analyzing all three factors, they were referred to as the (1) pleasant, (2) metallic, and (3) powerful factors. Each factor was confirmed to be composed of adjectives that were assumed to belong to that factor. Therefore, we assigned adjectives as expected to each factor to verify Verifications 1 and 2.

Next, a two-factor analysis of variance was performed on the evaluation values of the questionnaire using within-subjects design of creative experience (Before, After) and adjective pairs (12 items). Tables 1 to 3 show the average evaluation values for each sample. Significant differences were observed before and after the creative experience for Sample 1 ($F[1, 129] = 37.4, p < 0.001$), Sample 2 ($F[1, 129] = 6.419, p < 0.05$), and Sample 3 ($F[1, 129] = 5.618, p < 0.05$). Significant differences were also observed for the adjective pairs in Sample 1 ($F[11, 1419] = 174.6, p < 0.001$), Sample 2 ($F[11, 1419] = 128.5, p < 0.001$), and Sample 3 ($F[11, 1419] = 363.1, p < 0.001$). The interaction between each factor was significant in Samples 1 to 3. The following sample-specific findings were obtained:

- A) Sample 1 demonstrated significant interactions ($F[11, 1419] = 70.37, p < 0.001$). Next, a simple main-effect test was conducted. It was found that the adjectives with lower evaluation values were (1) easy–difficult ($p < 0.001$), (2) clear–muddy ($p < 0.001$), (3) simple–complex ($p < 0.001$), (4) pleasant–unpleasant ($p < 0.001$), and (5) smooth–rough ($p < 0.001$). The adjectives with improved evaluation values were (6) hard–soft ($p < 0.001$), (7) metallic–deep ($p < 0.001$), (8) shrill–calm ($p < 0.001$), (9) sharp–dull ($p < 0.001$), (10) clamorous–quiet ($p < 0.001$), (11) strong–weak ($p < 0.001$), and (12) powerful–unsatisfactory ($p < 0.001$).
- B) Sample 2 demonstrated significant interactions ($F[11, 1419] = 12.12, p < 0.001$). Next, a simple main-effect test was conducted. It was found that the adjectives with lower evaluation values were (1) easy–difficult

($p = 0.021$), (4) pleasant–unpleasant ($p < 0.001$), and (5) smooth–rough ($p = 0.012$). The adjectives with improved evaluation values were (6) hard–soft ($p = 0.002$), (7) metallic–deep ($p = 0.010$), (8) shrill–calm ($p = 0.001$), (9) sharp–dull ($p < 0.001$), and (10) clamorous–quiet ($p = 0.042$).

- C) Sample 3 demonstrated significant interactions ($F[11, 1419] = 21.58, p < 0.001$). Next, a simple main-effect test was conducted. It was found that the adjective with a lower evaluation value was (4) pleasant–unpleasant ($p = 0.025$). The adjectives with improved evaluation values were (8) shrill–calm ($p < 0.001$) and (9) sharp–dull ($p = 0.038$).

5. DISCUSSION

The analysis confirmed the significant differences in creative experience and impressions before and after creation, indicating that the participants' creative experience influenced the impressions of the samples. In other words, these findings suggest that creative experience may influence the way that music is listened to and the criteria that is used for evaluation. Next, we confirmed the following hypotheses regarding the enhancement of positive impressions via (Verification 1) a decrease in the evaluation of adjectives belonging to the pleasant factor or (Verification 2) an increase in the evaluation of adjectives belonging to the metallic and powerful factors.

The experimental results confirmed that there is a tendency toward confirming Verifications 1 and 2 in all samples depending on the creative experience. Verification 1 refers to a decrease in the evaluation values of the five pleasant factors (1), (2), (3), (4), and (5), and the evaluation values of Sample 1 (five items), Sample 2 (three items), and Sample 3 (one item) decreased significantly. Verification 2 refers to an increase in the evaluation values of the seven metallic and powerful factors (6), (7), (8), (9), (10), (11), and (12), and the evaluation values of Sample 1 (seven items), Sample 2 (five items), and Sample 3 (two items) increased significantly.

Furthermore, all adjective pairs with significant changes in rating values were changed to positive impressions. Significant differences were also found for the different adjectives. This suggested that the participants were evaluating their impressions of the music by differentiating between the different adjectives. In addition, the adjective pairs (4) pleasant–unpleasant, (8) shrill–calm and (9) sharp–dull exhibited significant differences that were common across all three samples. These adjectives may be metaphorical expressions that are susceptible to influence from the creative experience.

The participants who performed the creative activity in this experiment, experienced the editing of recorded unpitched sounds and the creation of electroacoustic music using a montage technique. The creative method that was used is similar to that used in Sample 1. The experimental results showed that Sample 1 had the highest number of adjectives that changed significantly. It is possible that the similarities in these artistic methods led to a clearer comparison with participants' own creative experiences. This in turn, might have led to an improved understanding of the ingenuity and effort that went into such works,

resulting in a positive impression. To verify this aspect, it would be pertinent to compare the case where the participants practiced the creation method of Sample 3, which had the smallest number of adjectives that changed significantly.

In this experiment, the participants answered the questionnaire after listening to the listening material of one work. The prediction is that there is a difference between the impression immediately after starting to listen to an unpleasant sound and the one impression after listening to it continuously from the viewpoint of habituation. For example, in addition to evaluation at one point in time, we should consider verification using a method [17] that allows continuous evaluation while listening to the work. Furthermore, the participants might find the SD method to be an easy-to-understand evaluation process, but its adjectives are too generalized and may lead to ambiguous evaluations of the work. We should develop an evaluation method that can appropriately evaluate the impression of electroacoustic and noise music streams.

Our results indicate that the vertex of Berlyne's inverted-U hypothesis (see Figure 2) for the individual participants shifted to the right under these conditions. This shift may indicate the process of accepting unpitched sounds or montages of sounds as "music" through the extension of the participants' sensibilities (see Figure 3). We believe that we were able to show the possibility that participation in creative activities is effective in drawing people to enjoy music that is perceived as "difficult."

6. FUTURE PROSPECTS

In the future, this study may be further developed from several additional perspectives to achieve more detailed analyses of these phenomena. These perspectives are summarized as follows:

- 1) The relationship between the characteristics of the created music and the characteristics of the music for which impressions change after the creation process may be examined. By investigating changes in the impressions obtained before and after the creation of a wide variety of music, we may be able to identify the effect of the created music on the impression of other music.
- 2) The effect of the duration of the creation process on the impression of previously created works may be investigated. In the present study, the duration of creation was one week. The length of this process could be varied to determine its effects on the participants' impressions of previously created works. Because the period of participation in the above-mentioned electroacoustic music-creation workshop is approximately one day, experimenting with the length of the creation process may clarify the significance of this workshop.
- 3) The effect of the participants' different levels of proficiency with music on their impressions of the previously created work may be verified. In this study, our analysis was conducted without considering the participants' proficiency in music. In the future, we may categorize participants by their proficiency level as those who do not usually listen to music, play a

musical instrument, or compose music. We will examine how the impressions of these participants change with respect to their proficiency level. Furthermore, if it is possible to determine the kind of music that the participants are proficient in, it may be possible to analyze the relationship between the participants' original musical preferences and their impressions of highly complex music.

- 4) The categorization of the participants' pre-creation impressions may be investigated, considering their rating values and the post-creation changes in those values. In this study, we comprehensively analyzed the differences in the evaluation values between the participants' impressions before and after the creation process. Next, we will examine how the participants' impressions of the work before the creation process affect their post-creation impressions. For example, if the positive impressions improved significantly even in a group with significantly low first impressions, it may be possible to advocate for the creation process as a meaningful activity even for those who are less likely to be familiar with related works of art.

We believe that through such multifaceted investigations, the relationship between the creation process and the resulting impressions of a work may be clarified in greater detail.

7. CONCLUSION

The authors quantitatively verified the increase in subjective acceptance toward music that is generally considered to be difficult. We investigated the receptiveness of participants toward music that may be considered difficult to listen to as it changed through the experience of creating this type of music.

The workshop operated by the authors encourages participants to explore diversity and creativity such that they are exposed to various styles of music, as well as to create music regardless of their current preferences. This process is highly relevant to STEAM education. The field of arts is less logical and objective and more difficult to quantitatively evaluate in comparison to STEM subjects. In STEAM education, it is expected that the arts will contribute to the expansion of the trainee's imagination and creativity.

Ordinary music has the function of enhancing group cohesion and imparting a sense of social belonging. However, electroacoustic music is thought to function differently from ordinary music, as exemplified by the results of this study. The authors believe that by developing the ideas stated in Section 6, it will be possible to clearly demonstrate the various effects of creating highly complex electroacoustic music.

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